
USE AND IMPACT OF INTERNET & SOCIAL MEDIA ON DIGITAL RESOURCES

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DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.7204018

Abstract:

Through this paper, we want to talk about social media (Umbrella of new media vs old media and Internet), although social media is not only impact in gold media also effected education method. Any corner of whole world who is not affected with social media as well as Internet. In the other terms is influence has become so widespread that every subject has its influence, so can remain untouched by Library science subject. Social media consists of networks which owe their existence to the new media. Social media deals with creation of virtual community there is no geographical boundary and no matter of Gender, and some factor involved like (Data, Device, Internet connection, Price etc.) some other factors are involved like utilization of social media in positive and negative purpose and spend total time on over it.

Keywords: Social media, Internet, Library Resource, Knowledge Sharing.

Introduction:

Media can be classified in 2 groups old media and new media or 2nd generation media. Social media is a part of New Media this media uses computer and Internet and deals with creation of virtual community like electronic mailing lists, bulletin boards, Wikis, Facebook, YouTube, LinkedIn, Blackboard and blogs etc. This media has no geographical boundaries and gender. Now days users are increasing day by day. It supports and extends social interactions in ways which combine both online and offline dimensions, secondly while social media can be used for outreach activities of existing communities, it can also cause the growth of problematic virtual communities

and thirdly social media enables collaborative work negating distance, this should lead to a reexamination of the nation of work in a networked world. Social networks are open representations of the contact between individuals and groups in a community. Social media analysis has been used, for example, to represent and analyze the organization structure of library users, identify key individuals, and suggest structural changes to improve unit performance. Virtual or online communities are groups of people connected through the internet and other information technology. The important part of modern society and give to life in various contexts social, educational, political and business. The communication

technologies and infrastructures used to support virtual communities have evolved with the internet and include electronic mailing lists, bulletin boards, Wikis, Facebook, YouTube, LinkedIn, Blackboard and blogs etc.

About social networking services told by Jeremy Hunsinger & Theresa Senft (2014) “The Meaning of the ‘Social media’ is a matter of debate: while some use the term quite narrowly to describe person to person relations on social networking services like Facebook and twitter, other use the term to signal socialization aspects of Web 2.0 sites in general....social media are networked information services, designed to support in depth social interaction, community formation, collaborative opportunities and collaborative works”

Characteristics of Social Media:

The main characteristics of new media are that they are interactive, two-way communication. The traditional media was analogue media, digital media are

inherently convergent, compressible and can be manipulated in various ways. Social media is a sub-set of new media. Social Media include applications such as Facebook, Twitter and You Tube, as well as LinkedIn. It also includes blogs and video blogs. In some sense all these mentioned media forms are networks connecting people in some way. These social media networks are changing the way people communicate, socialize, conduct business, educate, inform and entertain Themselves. They have also made inroads into domains such as politics and governance, once the bastion of traditional media such as print and broadcast.

Social Media Scenery:

According to <https://internetworldstats.com/stats3.htm> in 2022 internet usage in Asia (Internet users, Facebook subscribers & Population statistics for 35 countries and regions in Asia.)

INTERNET USERS AND 2022 POPULATION STATISTICS FOR ASIA						
Asia Region	Population (2022 Est.)	Pop. % World	Internet Users 31 July 2022	Penetration (% Pop.)	Internet % Users	Facebook 31 July 2022
Asia Only	4,352,169,960	54.9%	2,934,186,678	67.4%	53.6%	1,349,562,400
Rest of World	3,582,292,671	45.1%	2,538,869,058	70.9%	46.4%	1,891,307,977
All the world	7,934,462,631	100.0%	5,473,055,736	69.0%	100.0%	3,240,870,377

Notes:

- 1- Asia Population data are 2022 mid-year estimates
- 2- Asia Internet usage statistics in this table are for 31 July 2022.
- 3- The Facebook data are estimates also for 31 July 2022

- 4- For mythology, help and definitions, please see the site surfing guide.
- 5- Population estimates are based on figures from the United Nations Population Division and local official sources.

- 6- Internet usage numbers come mainly from data published by CNNIC,ITU, Facebook and other trustworthy sources.
- 7- Data from this table may be cited giving the due credit, giving the due credit to Internet World Stats.

Indian population was (2022) 1,402,228,175 and internet users were 833,710,000 in July 2022(59.5%) and Facebook subscribers were 515,800,000 July 2022 (38.2%) as per website study.

TRI REPORT 2020-21:

As per Telecom Regulatory Authority of India (TRI) has already mentioned

https://www.trai.gov.in/sites/default/files/Annual_Report_06042022_0.pdf Annual report 2020-21

Sl.	Subscriber	31 March 2020	31 March 2021
1	Internet Subscriber in India	743.19 million	825.30 million
2	Broadband subscriber	687.44million	778.09million
3	Wireless subscribers	1180.96 million	1201.20 million

This can also obtain from Digital resource.

Digital Resources Network:

YouTube:

YouTube is world largest 2nd search engine and on video web space world largest disruptor. According to CEO of google “**You Tube will be for bigger than TV**” through him now days On YouTube (Umbrella of New Media) you are the content creator, and you are viewer. In the old media it is not choice it is change. YouTube journey start from Tune in Hookup online dating site it is not making good response as per developer after that developed YouTube. The future of YouTube, most of users will be cord cutters users and next generation was cord Nevers (Never watch TV and not in future). YouTube has also done a good job on copyright, claim, offensive comment etc.

Facebook:

Now days Facebook known as Meta it is American multinational technology conglomerate based in Menlo Park California start in 4th Jan 2004 from Cambridge Massachusetts

known by Meta from 2021. Meta work come from Greek language. It means beyond denotes future purpose. Right now, it has approx. 2 billion active users around world. Its works on UGC (User Generated Content). It gives impower to person its open for all there is no matter of Gender, Geographical, religion etc. Facebook has ownership of Instagram and WhatsApp.

Impact of Social Media on Digital Resource (Rural and Urban India):

The Internet and Mobile association of India (IAMAI) and Kantar have released a report title ‘Internet in India’. **This report has taken on the ICUBE 2021 study and denotes a amazing surge in the number of internet users in rural India.**

According to the report, at present there are 692 million active Internet users in India and much of growth continuous to be driven by rural India where 351 million users of using the internet with 37 per cent penetration. **Alternatively, urban India seems to have hit a raised ground where**

341 million users are 69 per cent using the internet.

Finally report indicates that there will be 900 million internet users in India by 2025 led by rural development. Here report say that Goa has the maximum internet penetration while Bihar has the lowest.

Report says global pandemic witnessed a record of 51 per cent boost in digital transactions in just two years from 230 million in 2019 in India,.

The report also highlighted the use cases of users, entertainment, communication and the social media are the top three activities engaged in by internet users across India.

Conclusion:

The highest reason for the new media to come forward is because it is not slow and disengaged like the old media, that's why it is running ahead of the old traditional media, there is no more trouble to use the new media, and you must go anywhere. You can also grasp from it, but old media does not give all this, new media empowers you and gives you full opportunity to raise your voice, new media gives you full opportunity to comment, like and dislike, For example, we subscribe to many channels on YouTube, but if we see it is only two to five daily, in the same way there are 1250 channels of current media but only 10 come on TV remote, out of which only four to seven are favorite. What we see is the only and only empire of “content” in today, content is the king of social media. In the same way, the YouTube platform provide details to content developer regarding content user like, psychology, demographic, number of uses, gender and average watch time of the user of the content but does not disclose the personal information of the content

developer all this means new media provides today.

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19. [Facebook World Stats and Penetration in the World - Facebook Statistics \(internetworldstats.com\)](#)